

**THE REGISTRY OF PATENTS
SINGAPORE**

**THE PATENTS ACT
(CHAPTER 221)**

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT OF PATENT

In accordance with section 35 of the Patents Act, it is hereby certified that a patent having the P-No. 162009 [WO 2009/078809] has been granted in respect of an invention having the following particulars:

Title : QUANTUM TUNNELING PHOTODETECTOR
ARRAY

Application Number : 201003632-5

Date of Filing : 18 December 2007

Priority Data : -

Name of Inventor(s) : MICHALEWICZ, MAREK, T.

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Date of Grant : 31 December 2012

Dated this 31st day of December 2012.

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